

THE IMPORTANT ROLE OF WOMEN IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY

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"If you want something said, ask a man; if you want something done, ask a woman" Margaret Thatcher

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Abstract: This article explains how women function in our nation's society. In contrast to historical discrimination and violence, everyone is treated equally in today's stable society, and women's possibilities and potential are greatly respected. Today, our nation's legislative framework has been reinforced to ensure gender equality and to give men and women equal rights and opportunities. Women work well in any profession, are fully aware of their obligations, and contribute to the nation's progress and citizens' well-being. As mentioned in the article, the interests of women cannot be imagined separately from the interests of the family, neighborhood and society. The comprehensive solution of these issues, raising the state policy to a higher level in this regard was recognized as the main task for the development of the society.

Key words: Constitution, equal rights, human rights, gender violence, social and political relations, implementation, legal interest, supporting, social and political life.

Introduction

Half of the population of our planet is made up of women and girls, which means half of humanity's potential. From this point of view, gender equality is one of the most important human rights, and it plays an important role in ensuring peace and harmony in society, and realizing human potential based on sustainable development. It has already been proven that increasing the participation of women in society increases labor productivity and ensures economic growth. Nevertheless, humanity still has to do a lot of work to fully ensure the equality of women and men based on their rights and opportunities. First of all, it is necessary to end all forms of gender violence, to create equal conditions for education, health care, and access to economic resources for women and girls, as well as men and children. In addition, it is necessary to create equal opportunities for their participation in political life. This also applies to the issue of women finding work and being appointed to leadership positions. The development of any state and society is based on a number of factors. In this process, the issue of women, their participation in social and political relations, the fact that their rights and freedoms are ensured in practice is considered an important index of the development of states and democracy. Already, a woman and her role in the life of society have always been an important criterion.

Professional activity is one of the main areas of individual self-realization. Today, almost everyone can choose their dream profession and achieve it. The word "almost" is not accidental here, because the world is still divided into "female" and "male" professions. People who do not mind "their" business may encounter stereotypes and prejudices. However, men still have the right to the job they want, although there are some difficulties, for women it is a little different. In Russia there is a list of professions prohibited for women, that is, women are already limited in their choice of professional activities. Women are much more likely than men to face socio-economic and political problems. Such difficulties are due, for example, to the personnel policy of management, in which women are limited in their professional development or, for example, the professional qualifications of men are recognized more often, which leads to tougher competition. Another problem is the lack of opportunities for women to express themselves in professional activities and realize their knowledge, skills and experience. The process of a professional career is the result of an individual's self-realization, conscious exercise and professional progress, guaranteeing an acceptable level of professional self-esteem, social recognition and a certain quality of life. In addition, a career can become an incentive for an employee's professional development and the realization of her personal potential. (Kotomanova, 2013) The vast majority of women in senior positions say that a professional career is a certain outcome in business professional activity that a working person strives for

Methods

"Achieving gender equality, expanding the rights and opportunities of women and girls remains an unfinished task, and this problem is a huge problem in the field of human rights today," says UN Secretary-General Antonio Guterres. By the way, the international organization that deals with this issue the most is undoubtedly the UN. Clause 1 of the Charter of the Organization reflects the need for international cooperation to respect and promote human rights and fundamental freedoms regardless of race, gender, language and religion. In the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, gender equality is an important part of international law in the field of human rights. This document, adopted by the UN General Assembly on December 10, 1948, states that "all human beings are born free and equal with their dignity and rights."

The role of women, their political and legal culture is of particular importance in the chain of development of Uzbekistan as a state and society, which has a worthy place among the countries of the world and in the international community. The 2022–2026 National Program aims to increase women's participation in all facets of the nation's social, political, and economic life. A thorough plan of action has been prepared for 2022–2026 with the goal of implementing the National Program on Increasing the Activity of Women in All Aspects of the Nation's Economic, Political, and Social Life in 2022–2023. The wide-ranging reforms carried out in our country to raise the value of women are of course of decisive importance as the legal frameworks in this regard have been created and are being regularly improved. In particular, Article 46 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "Women and men have equal rights" serves as the main legal basis for systemic reforms in our country to ensure gender equality and increase the role of women in society and state management. In order to implement these tasks, the strategy of achieving gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 was approved by the Senate of the Oliy Majlis.

As a logical continuation of the efforts, the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for the period of 2022-2026 envisages a number of goals and tasks for realizing the rights and legal interests of women. In the 69th goal called "Supporting women, ensuring their active participation in the life of society", including creating an environment of intolerance towards oppression and violence against women in society, promoting the rights and legal interests of women.

Results

In the process of today's globalization, the place and role of women is more important than ever in the matter of forming an active civil position of the new generation in relation to any conditions. Therefore, the main content of the reforms is to support women to come up with new ideas and initiatives, to ensure their active participation in the efforts, changes and social-political processes implemented in our country. It must be recognized that in recent years, the implementation of comprehensive measures aimed at ensuring the rights and legal interests of women, strengthening their role in society, and supporting the family institution has reached a new level of quality.

Uzbekistan joined all the main international documents that protect women from any discrimination and humiliation. It should be noted that more than 30 decrees and decisions and government decisions were adopted on the direct initiative of the head of state in the issues of women's support.

These regulatory legal documents are particularly important with the following positive aspects: *first*, a new state body specialized in working professionally with families and women - State Committee for Family and Women was established; *secondly*, the main directions of the unified state policy in the field of supporting women, protecting their rights and legal interests were defined; *thirdly*, a new mechanism of working with women was defined - the practice of working with women in neighborhoods in a targeted and targeted manner; *fourthly*, in order to ensure women's rights and protect them from oppression and violence, new legal mechanisms were introduced - supervision of the prosecution authorities over the implementation of legislation in this field; *fifthly*, a new package of state guarantees and benefits was introduced for women to get an education, engage in scientific and creative activities; *sixthly*, the existing mechanisms to support women's business activities and help them to get a decent marriage have been improved; *seventhly*, a new system aimed at protecting women's health, early detection and prevention of diseases specific to women

was introduced; *eighth*, new mechanisms of communication with women are being introduced and new, effective communication platforms have been established.

Let's talk about some problems in women's careers. Gradually, a career may acquire some features. This is due to stereotypes attributed to women that prevent them from performing at work, as well as due to the personality changes that women invariably experience as they advance in their careers. To begin with, there are some factors that can influence it:

Business qualities	Psychological qualities	Communication abilities
<p>As women take on more responsibility and higher-stakes projects, they often have to become more efficient and results-oriented. This can lead to a more assertive and direct communication style, a heightened focus on deadlines, and potentially even a less collaborative approach at times (depending on the pressure). They might also develop a stronger sense of self-reliance and become less hesitant to delegate tasks. Think of it as a necessary adaptation to succeed in a demanding environment.</p>	<p>As women navigate the challenges of a male-dominated or even just competitive workplace, they often develop greater emotional resilience. They learn to manage stress effectively, handle criticism constructively, and perhaps even cultivate a thicker skin. Their confidence might grow exponentially as they achieve milestones and gain recognition. However, the constant need to prove themselves can also lead to increased self-doubt or perfectionism in some cases. It's a double-edged sword.</p>	<p>To succeed in leadership roles, women often refine their communication skills significantly. They become more adept at presenting ideas clearly and persuasively, negotiating effectively, and building consensus. They might become more comfortable speaking up in meetings and asserting their opinions. They might also learn to tailor their communication style to different audiences and situations – a skill crucial for navigating workplace dynamics</p>

What about the actual personality changes? It's hard to say "invariably" because every woman's experience is unique, but here are some potential shifts we might see:

- Increased assertiveness: a move away from hesitancy to a more confident and direct communication style.
- Enhanced self-confidence: success breeds confidence, and overcoming challenges builds resilience.
- Greater emotional regulation: the ability to manage stress and navigate difficult interpersonal situations effectively.
- Improved strategic thinking: a shift from a focus on immediate tasks to a broader understanding of organizational goals and strategies.
- Stronger decision-making skills: the ability to make timely and effective decisions under pressure.
- Increased resilience: the ability to bounce back from setbacks and challenges.

However, it's also important to note that these changes aren't necessarily positive in every aspect.

Discussion

Attention to women has risen to the level of real public policy: its legal and institutional foundations have been radically improved. Activities to ensure gender equality in our country, increase the role of women in social and political life: improvement of legislation on women's rights; improvement of the institutional framework for the protection of women; raising public awareness of gender equality and women's rights; consists of the main directions, such as training of officials responsible for ensuring their compliance in the practice of law enforcement, on the basis of relevant legal norms. Ensuring gender equality and expanding the rights and opportunities of all women is consistent with reforms aimed at ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men in our country. Within the framework of the implementation of this goal, the elimination of all forms of discrimination against women, all forms of violence against them, including human trafficking, sexual exploitation and other forms of exploitation, early

marriages and forced marriages, women's political, providing equal opportunities for their comprehensive participation in all stages of economic and social life and leadership in decision-making, comprehensive medical and sanitary assistance in the field of reproductive health care to provide general access to health services and 9 similar tasks.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that it is necessary to take into account the aspirations and abilities of our women and girls who are studying and working, to continue their activities in society with men in an organic and harmonious way, and to expand their opportunities.

There is no doubt that the reforms to fully ensure the participation of women in the management of society and state affairs, and to support them from a socio-economic and legal point of view are an example of social justice in ensuring gender equality and equal rights in our country. It is a reasonable strategy to protect the rights and interests of our women and increase their social and political activity in our society. Because, let's not forget, "The education of the future is in the hands of our women scientists". In addition, for the first time in the world experience, the position of women's activist was introduced in order to work with women's issues on the development of entrepreneurship, employment of the population, reduction of poverty in a separate, comprehensive and targeted manner

References

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2018 No. PF-5325 on "Measures to fundamentally improve activities in the field of supporting women and strengthening the family institution".
2. Decree No. PF-81 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 1, 2022 "On measures to improve the system of working with families and women, and supporting the community and religious".
3. Decree No. PF-87 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 7, 2022 "On measures to further accelerate work on systematic support of families and women".
4. D. Bazarova (Ph.D., professor). "Increasing social and political activity of women in Uzbekistan is the demand of the times". - Tashkent: TDUU, 2019.
5. Kotomanova O.V. Professional career as a path for a woman's personal development // Bulletin of BSU. Education. Personality. Society. 2013.
6. Kotomanova O.V. Features of a woman's professional career // Bulletin of BSU. Education. Personality. Society. 2008
7. Kossek E. E., Buzzanell P. M. Women's career equality and leadership in organizations: Creating an evidence-based positive change // Human Resource Management. – 2018..